

Newsletter from
The Department of Library and Information Science
Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvavur

Prof. M. Krishnan, Hon. Vice Chancellor, CUTN giving a memento of DLIS fraternity to Prof. S. Ravi on his retirement on 30th October 2022

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HoD's Note

I'm excited to inform that the third issue of *Bibliophile's* fourth volume has been published. Putting on a display the academic, cultural, and other activities that took place during the time has been one of the department's essential functions. Newspaper clippings, celebrations of various festivals, student and faculty accomplishments, departmental activities, scheduled events, and notable successes are all included in this issue. It is without a doubt an excellent platform for Department students to excel in editorial work where they can showcase their abilities and capabilities by providing information and developing the *Bibliophile*. I would like to thank all the students, researchers, and teachers on behalf of the Department and congratulate the editorial team for producing such a magnificent e-newsletter.

Dr. Akhandanand Shukla

Student Editor's note

A person who has great love for books; that's the meaning of the word *Bibliophile*. A good book is a man's best friend. but nowadays people tend to become friends with the digital world and electronic media. The newsletter *bibliophile* is a mere reminder that the era of reader friendly books can't be substituted by any modern techs. I feel very happy to be in the position of the student editor of *Bibliophile*. I would also like to acknowledge that this Newsletter is the product of the regular work by a well established team from the Department of Library and Information Science.

I candidly thank Dr. K. G. Sudhier, faculty editor for entrusting me with such a great responsibility. I also thank each and every one of my friends in the editorial team as well as to those who contributed to this issue of the Newsletter.

Abhishek M

Faculty Editor's page**One Nation, One Subscription (ONOS) Policy**

Dr. K. G. Sudhier

Scholarly journals play an important role in knowledge dissemination since researchers unanimously use journals as the primary mode to communicate their research findings. India, as one of the world's leading producers of scientific information, Indian researchers and research institutions collectively spend around 15 billion rupees (USD 200 million) on journal subscriptions for scholarly literature every year.

Access to scholarly journals is a critical debate among Indian academics, and there are long-standing discussions in India about how to enhance the accessibility of scholarly output to empower the researchers with knowledge and improve the quality of the current research of the country. One major initiative is the OA policy (DST, 2014) which the two major science funding agencies jointly introduced, the Department of Science and Technology (DST) and the Department of Biotechnology (DBT), Government of India. Another significant development is a proposal called 'one nation, one subscription' (Koley & Lala, 2022).

An official statement from the Ministry of Education says that "The One Nation One Subscription intends to sign national licenses with most of the prominent STEM publishers and database producers of the world whose contents are already being subscribed by various institutions of higher education and research organizations either

directly or through government-funded consortia". More significantly, the government has also proposed to buy bulk subscriptions to all the important scientific journals across the world, and provide everyone in India free access to them. The proposals have been made in the draft 5th Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (STIP) policy. This policy instrument aims to establish a centrally negotiated system to subscribe to journals, and eventually, all institutions in India will be able to access necessary resources.

Resources from 70 publishers recommended by the Planning and Execution Committee (PEC) are being taken into consideration by the core committee for the first phase of ONOS.

A statement from the education ministry reads: "The ONOS intends to sign national licenses with most of the prominent STEM publishers and database producers of the world whose contents are already being subscribed by various institutions of higher education and research organizations either directly or through government-funded consortia".

Features

- Government has remarkably proposed to purchase a majority of important scientific journals all across the world and provide it to all Indians free of cost.
- It has been proposed to buy 3000 to 4000 high-impact journals and an estimated budget of 2000 crore to 3000 crore has been planned to subscribe to these journals.
- All kinds of data generated will be stored in the Science, Technology and Innovation Observatory.
- This observatory will provide data to publicly funded research through 'FAIR' (Fair, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).
- The policy also proposes to take proactive steps to improve the standard of Indian journals and it will also put a serious check on the publication of fake journals.
- It has been anticipated that India will become Atmanirbhar in S&T through this policy.

Benefits

All educational and research institutions, including universities, colleges and research organizations, as well as every person in the nation are expected to benefit from the move, the ministry said, pointing in addition to the benefit of library access in remote areas if technical solutions can be found. Unhindered access to scientific knowledge would narrow gaps in access among Indian institutions and would mean that smaller institutions or those with fewer resources would not be at disadvantage in securing access to a wide range of journals. Better access to resources would also increase researcher productivity and quality. The ONOS policy for scientific journals could be a turning point for the scientific community and individual researchers.

This issue of the *Bibliophile* reaches you in the new year 2023. I thank all my colleagues at the DLIS, the Student Editor, and the Members of the Editorial team for their support and efforts in bringing out this issue. The *Bibliophile* will continue to be a medium for promoting the activities of DLIS as well as the creativeness of the students and faculty.

Wish you all a very productive and fulfilling 2023!

K. G. Sudhier

Release of Previous Issues of Bibliophile

Bibliophile Volume 04 Issue 01 handed over to Prof. J. P. Singh Joorel, Director, INFLIBNET Centre by Prof. S. Ravi in the presence Dr. K. G. Sudhier and Dr. Akhandanand Shukla.

Bibliophile's special edition (on Prof. S. Ravi) handed over to Dr. V. Thiruvalluvan, Vice Chancellor, Tamil University, Thanjavur by Prof. G. Ravindran, Dean, School of Communication, CUTN.

EDITORIAL TEAM

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The DLIS family welcomes Dr. C. Ranganathan

Dr. C. Ranganathan, is working as an Associate Professor at the Department of Library & Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvavur since 22nd November 2022. Before CUTN, he worked as a faculty at the Department of Library and Information Science, Bharathidasan University for more than 13 years and was an associate professor for the last three years. He has served in the field for a long time since 2000.

He did his MSc Chemistry (1994) from Bharathidasan university, and M.Ed (1996), MLIS (1998), M.Phil.(1999) from Annamalai University. In 2016, he received his Ph. D. from Bharathidasan University. He has fulfilled various responsibilities including being the chairman of the board of studies since October 2021 and was a member of the Standing Committee on Academic Affairs in Bharathidasan University. He has served as a Co-ordinator for UGC-sponsored faculty development programmes and short-term courses. He has a research experience of 16 years and has guided many research scholars and PG students in Bharathidasan University and Alagappa University (DDE). His areas of specialization and research interest are Information Processing and Retrieval, Classification, Cataloguing and Indexing Research Methodology, User Studies, Information Seeking Behaviour, Knowledge Management, Electronic Resource Management, and Metric Studies: Bibliometrics, Scientometrics, Informetrics, Webometrics. He has published more than 94 publications in national and international research journals, book chapters, monographs, and manuals and has two books to his credit. Besides this, he has attended more than 140 conferences, seminars, workshops, etc at regional, national, and international levels and has published 179 conference papers. He has continued to make valuable contributions to the discipline and for its development.

Dr. K. G. Sudhier elected as the Vice President of IASLIC

Dr. K. G. Sudhier, Assistant Professor, Department of Library and Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu has been elected as Vice- President, Indian Association of Special Libraries and Information Centres (IASLIC), Kolkata. The IASLIC, one of the oldest professional association in the country was established in 1955 as a non-profit national organisation that supports development in the entire field of special librarianship in India.

Always a Teacher...

An Interview with Prof. J. P. Singh Joorel, the INFLIBNET Director

Mr. Saba Shreeram P (II M.Lib.I.Sc.) and Ms. Nayanthara S (PhD scholar) interviewing Prof. J. P. Singh Joorel

Nayanthara : From your journey as a Dean and Head of the Jammu University to the Director of INFLIBNET, we are curious to know about your journey, about the change of roles and all.

Prof. Joorel : See, for a teacher, in his/her life there are different stages. In the beginning, teachers are always involved in the teaching, research but as for the institutions, academic institutions, there are three part in the institutions. Firstly, the students. So generally any educational institute is as well as only for the students for imparting their education. Now, to impart the education we need teachers. So the second part is teachers. To support these two we need examination system. Now, to support these three, or manage three, we have the administration system, i.e. Registrar, Controller and Vice Chancellor's, right? It is called administration, right?

So these are the four components of an institution. Now, the best person who can manage any institution will be decided from his/her academic background. So it means , based on the experience he must have the expertise in teaching, he must have expertise in the whole administrative stuff, all the departments, the function of the institutions at the university level. And then only if a person have expertise to manage their own institutions, they can manage or they can lead any higher education system in India. So I always advocate for the teachers that whatever they are teaching their subjects to the students they must also know how to handle any situation in the University. How to handle the day to do work in the department, right? There are other things.

And then beyond your institution, you also must know what is happening in the scenario of the higher education in the country, what are the policies of higher education, what are the programs of higher education in central level as well as your state level..

Whether you agree or disagree with these policies, that is up to you.

But you must know what are the different policies and programs. For example, suppose you know all the features, programs and policies of the government, of any government, especially with respect to higher education, either you agree or disagree. If you disagree, you are in a position to tell that you are against these policies. You can recommend if you feel that there is a better way to enact a policy, right? Because you're a teacher.

You are building the nation through training the students, who are the future of the country. So we must know what is happening in our country, especially in higher education; and beyond that too, what is the whole requirement of the country, what are the needs of the society, how this can be solved? Take for example, this University, which is situated in a rural area. Suppose I'm being appointed as the Vice Chancellor of this University, if you say that my role is to provide the best facilities for students in terms of the hostel facilities, the library, the teachers, in terms of the other facilities and even to evaluate the teachers also, I do agree. But at the same time, as a Vice Chancellor, my role is even beyond the university . It also extends to the needs of the rural background, the ways in which my university can serve my surrounding villages so that their livelihood can be uplifted. I might suggest my department to collect a raw material or a product on a daily basis, not from the market, but to train the farmers of the surrounding rural areas to produce some useful products so that the economic conditions of that area can be uplifted through small scale trade.

Saba : Thank you Sir. You are working very closely with librarians as an INFLIBNET Director. May I ask you from an objective point of view because you are not exactly from this profession so I can get an objective view on what you think about the profession as a librarianship?

Prof. Joorel : It is a very noble profession and as far as the service is concerned, without the libraries, dreaming of an institute is not possible. So library is a core for any institution. I can say that it is the foremost thing without any doubt. Now, there are two things of concern. One is the resources in the library and other is the human resources to manage the resources.

Prof. J. P. Singh Joorel interacting with the students and scholars of the Department

We must train the human resources in such a way that they should be able to provide the materials required by the user, even if the resources are unavailable in the library; but to another level, by collecting materials from nearby sources. They should be able to provide and share other resources of the different levels also. That's the first thing.

And second thing because the advancement of technology nowadays we need the LIS professionals who are fully equipped and trained with the latest technology as well as the vertical knowledge of the LIS (i.e.) What is the copyright? How can I provide the access of the books in my library to the students? Creating the digital library, creating institutional repository, providing the remote access facility, training the faculty members in creating the e-content, it's dissemination, it's hosting, right? And also you can say, I have no idea whether what is happening in your city? You follow or not? In the beginning of the session is the duty of the LIS professionals to go for the orientation of their residence in their institution that we have these resources available in my library and how we can use these resources for the betterment of the students.

Nayanthara : Thank you, sir. And you have talked about the syllabi of DRTC and everything and majorly INFLIBNET focus on librarians and libraries. May I ask if you have some vision for LIS students from the grassroot level.

Prof. Joorel : Generally that is because the courses in curriculum come under UGC. Most of the universities are following that. But they are also free to incorporate some advanced topics. So I mostly advocate and I also urge upon the faculty members of the institutions to modify their curriculum. We can do the requirement in few days and come out from the existing syllabus so that students can be trained better so that they can get easily prepared for the future.

Saba : One last question. Can we have a message for our LIS students here from an honorable person like you.

Prof. Joorel : All the best to all the LIS students and I'm happy to welcome them in our INFLIBNET Centre. Whenever they would like to visit us, we provide all the facilities to the LIS students of this University, best of luck. Thank you.

Saba & Nayantara : Thanks a lot Sir.

Libraries also have a history to tell

Libraries have a great place in the history of the development of human civilization. It can be traced back to a history of about three thousand years. It began in the seventh century B.C. in Mesopotamia. But at the same time, it should be noted that the history of libraries has not been essentially consistent. Libraries have a history of being destroyed faster than they were built. But both of these actions have occurred throughout history.

Even that library in Mesopotamia was destroyed by the Babylonians back then. The cycle of destruction that began then has now reached the 1990s, when Serbian forces destroyed Bosnia's most important library. This book tells the equally fascinating and unusual history of libraries. - *The Library-A Fragile History*, written by Andrew Pettegree and Arthur der Weduwen.

RIYA V.C
II M.Lib.I.Sc.

The Library : A Fragile History
by/ Andrew Pettegree and
Arthur der Weduwen : Hachette
Publication

Ancient libraries in Mesopotamia had 3500 clay tablets. Back then, knowledge was recorded on clay tablets. Later, the instrument called the book went through many evolutions. For a long time, they were limited to the exclusive possession of kings and religious scholars. It also stood as a symbol of flamboyance. Such personal collections of books came to be known as libraries. A revolutionary change was recorded in the history of books and libraries when printing technology was discovered in 1450 AD. Even then, they were inaccessible to the common man. They continued to be among the nobles, scholars, and priests. The number of books in their collection kept increasing. A professor's library in seventeenth-century France contained more books than the university library where he worked. It is not even imaginable today.

Another revolution took place in the 1930s with the advent of cheap paperback book editions. It was a form of decentralization. We are now witnessing its continuity. By 1900, public libraries were established in the United States along with university libraries. This has been replicated around the world. Early libraries had space only for scholarly books. In the 20th century, libraries began to accept novels, stories, etc. Now, the digital technology revolution is changing the nature of books and libraries. The authority of the book has always been an enigma. Books and libraries have always had a great influence on the determination of politics. There is so much strange and shocking history behind the institution called the library. This is an integral writing that seeks out all of this.

Departmental Activities

OPEN ACCESS WEEK 2022

The Department of Library and Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu has organised a special online lecture as part of the International Open Access Week 2022 on 26th October 2022 through Google Meet. Dr. Anup Kumar Das, Documentation Officer, Centre for Studies in Science Policy, JNU New Delhi was invited as the speaker. He delivered the lecture on "Open for Climate Justice: A Brief Overview of Digital Library on Green Mobility (DLGM)". Dr. Anup Kumar Das started the lecture by giving some introductory ideas about climate change and its effects on people and society.

He explained that the simple solution to this issue is to reduce carbon emissions, and that in order to do so, an urgent need to reform the current transportation system is needed. In this framework, the current state of e-mobility in India was discussed, and it is clear that India is on the cusp of a revolutionary change in electric mobility. The resource person also mentioned government initiatives in this area. The first initiative was the content of the Green Mobility Digital Library (DLGM).

It is a website for getting e-vehicle information as well as other government policies on e-mobility. The aim, features, and resources of E-Amrit, a similar type of portal created by NITI Ayog, were also noted. Shoonya, the zero-pollution mobility campaign with its many tool kits, the creation of an EV charging station in various parts of the country, and the adaptation of EVs in the

Indian army sector had all become topics of discussion. The lecture session also included some state efforts on the issue. The lecture was coordinated by Dr. Anila Sulochana, Assistant Professor, Department of Library and Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvavur, and attended by 28 participants. The lecture session ended with a formal vote of thanks proposed by Dr. Anila Sulochana.

SWACHHATA PAKHWADA

The DLIS, CUTN has organised a cleanliness drive “Clean and Green Program” under the umbrella of Swachhata Pakhwada 2022 on 23rd September 2022 (4.00 pm) at Central Library Premises. Faculty Members, Scholars, PG Students and Staff of the department participated in the cleanliness drive. The program was coordinated by Dr. Taddi Murali, Departmental Coordinator for Swachh Bharat Abhiyan. A total of 19 persons participated in the program.

The Clean and Green program aims to protect and care for the environment by engaging the community in leading an environmentally conscious lifestyle. Clean campus promote hygiene, It improves hygiene levels on campus and also helps to reduce the spread of sickness; maintaining a clean campus environment sets a good example for students. Cleanliness encourages learners to take pride in their campus, which makes them less likely to drop litter, and as such, they will potentially make a bigger effort to maintain their environment. Cleanliness gives rise to a good character by keeping the body, mind, and soul clean and peaceful. Maintaining cleanliness is an essential part of healthy living because cleanliness alone helps improve our personalities by keeping us clean externally and internally.

PUSTAK PUJA

The Department of Library and Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu has celebrated “Pustaka Puja” on 4th October 2022 at 10.00 am in the department. Faculty Members, Scholars, PG Students and Staff of the department participated in the “Pustaka Puja” Celebrations. The program was organised by Dr. Akhandanand Shukla, Head of the department and Ms. Chithra M, Office

Staff along with PG students of the department. Saraswati Pooja is an important festival in South India, where it is either observed on the sixth day or on the ninth or tenth day of the Navaratri festival, depending on the state in which the festival is celebrated, a day when children are blessed and first introduced to the world of letters. On the day of South Saraswati Pooja, children also offer notebooks and stationery items to the goddess. As the day is considered most auspicious for beginning learning in any field, young children take their first step towards education.

NATIONAL LIBRARIAN'S DAY

The Department of Library and Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu, has organised a National Librarians Day Celebration on the occasion of Padma Shri Dr. S. R. Ranganathan's 130th Birth Anniversary Celebration on August 16, 2022, at 11 a.m. through Google Meet. On this occasion, the department has invited Dr. Vijayakumar M., University Librarian, Pondicherry University, Puducherry, as a special guest to deliver the theme talk "Five Laws of Library Science in the Present Context."

Dr. Vijayakumar M. talked about his experience in incorporating the five laws into various aspects of librarianship. Dr. Vijayakumar expressed how five laws are important to libraries, and each law was explained with its implications, that is, how these laws will be applied in the current context.

He emphasised how important it is to procure resources for differently-abled users. The importance of library location, rules and regulations, incorporating ICT, and maintaining an updated OPAC to save users' time were discussed in detail. He gave some innovative ideas like the concept of a garden library, a terrace library, meditation rooms, a cafeteria, and refreshing areas that will help attract users to the library. There was an active Q&A session after the lecture where Dr. Vijayakumar answered the students' queries.

"A modern librarian, who has faith in the law that 'BOOKS ARE FOR USE,' is happy only when his readers make his shelves constantly empty. It is not the books that go out that worry him. It is the stay-at-home volumes that perplex and depress him". – Dr. SR. Ranganathan

VEDARANYAM VISIT

The faculties and staff of DLIS led by the Hon. Vice Chancellor and senior faculties of CUTN, have conducted a visit to the most famous and a place of historic importance, Vedaranyam beach and premises. Vedaranyam is considered to be the point of the civil disobedience movement, 1930's, led by C. Rajagopalachari. The visit was planned as a part of the Azadi ka Amrit Mahotsav.

Felicitation Programme for Prof. S. Ravi

"Teaching is a very noble profession that shapes the character, caliber, and future of a person. If people remember a good teacher, it will be the greatest honour for that teacher."

The greatest honour a teacher gets is the kind words and gifts given to him by his loved ones during his academic career, which will be one of the memories he will never forget. Department of

Library and Information Science, Central University of Tamilnadu, Thiruvarur, and Annamalai University organised the felicitation ceremony on October 30, 2022, celebrating the four decades of success and journey of Prof. S. Ravi's academic career. This programme was conducted at the Guest House Conference Hall, Central University of Tamilnadu, Thiruvarur.

It was a full-day programme. The function started at 10:00 a.m. The felicitation ceremony was attended by Prof. S. Ravi's family, friends, former students, department faculty, and students. Prof. S. Thanushkodi (Dean, Faculty of Arts Professor and Head, DLIS Alagappa University, Karaikkudi) welcomed everyone to the program. Prof. R. Saranagani, University Librarian and Head (i/c) DLIS Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, provided an overview of the Felicitation. The next section was about honouring the guests. Presidential Address was done by Prof. M. Nagarajan (former Dean, Faculty of Arts and Fine Arts Professor and Head, DLIS, Annamalai University. Prof. T.D. Kemparaju (former Vice-Chancellor of Bengaluru North University) was the Guest of Honor. The following section was about presenting citations and awards to Prof. S. Ravi as well as LIS professionals, friends, and relatives. He then accepted the citations and awards. Dr. K. G. Sudhier (Assistant Professor, DLIS, CUTN) did the vote of thanks at the end of the section.

After the lunch break, the programme started at 3 pm. Dr. Akhandanand Shukla (Head of DLIS, CUTN) welcomed everyone to the afternoon session. Following that, a dignitary honouring ceremony was conducted. The Presidential Address was given by Prof. M. Krishnan (Hon'ble Vice Chancellor, CUTN). The next section was release of Souvenir and Festschrift Volume and the special Issue on Prof. S. Ravi's Bibliophile Newsletter from the DLIS, CUTN. Prof. RM. Kathiresan (Hon'ble Vice Chancellor, Annamalai University), Prof. V. Thiruvalluvan (Hon'ble Vice Chancellor, Tamil University, Thanjavur), and Prof. Ravinder Kumar Chadha (Former Additional Secretary Parliament of India, Lok Sabha, New Delhi) were addressed by special address. The Felicitation Address was delivered by Prof. Sulochana Shekhar (Registrar (i/c), CUTN), Prof. S. Nagarajan (Controller of Examinations (i/c), CUTN), Prof. Srinivasa Ragavan (Controller of Examinations (i/c), Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli), Shri. CMA.V. Palani (Finance Officer, CUTN), Dr. R. Parameswaran. Prof. S. Ravi accepted the citation. The programme ended with a vote of thanks by Prof. R. Sevukan (Professor, DLIS, Pondicherry University).

"A good teacher is a good friend." This statement is undeniably true since Prof. S. Ravi was always been a good teacher, good friend, good father, good colleague, good husband, good grandfather and it goes on. On all sides, he is a very good person. The Felicitation Program invited Prof. S. Ravi, LIS Professionals, Students, Friends, and Family to share their blessed experiences, such as his academic career, personality, and so on, and everybody were eager to compliment Prof. S. Ravi, his wife, and other guests. The programme concluded beautifully as it provided much memories to all participants.

Little thing called HAPPINESS

What is Life? Why do we Live?
 People say we live only once but in my
 view
 we live every day and die only once
 Yes! We live daily.
 We wake up with a lot of to-do things
 Are we completing it at the end of the
 day?
 We do make plans and
 we do procrastinate it as well!
 Here, I have used the word 'DO'
 because it emphasizes.
 We live our life on routine
 What we do is live our life to the fullest.
 Why shouldn't we live with happiness?
 We do have to live to make progress in
 our life.
 We live in every little things,
 Those little things may feel big
 -when we look back,
 At the end of the day
 all we want is a smile on our face.
 We live for happiness.
 Despite living our own life,
 we shall spread happiness;

ARCHANA S
 I M.Lib.I.Sc.

We can live the life the way we want to,
 Happy or sad; love or hate,
 It's all up to us.
 I do believe that happiness is within
 ourselves,
 Live for those little things,
 Because happiness is found
 -in those little things too,
 The so called little things
 are the memories that we cherish.
 And those little things are helping
 others;
 to make others and yourself happy,
 When little gestures make us happy,
 Why to stop ourselves making those
 gestures?
 A smile can make someone's day,
 Be happy, live happy, share happiness!
 That's the thing we all are looking for
 in others and ourselves!
 Enjoy doing little things,
 Create happy memories!
SMILE!! it costs nothing.

"Sometimes, it's better to bunk class and enjoy with friends, because now, when I
 look back, Marks never make me laugh, but memories do."

(Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam)

Adios Prof. S. Ravi from DLIS, CUTN

An official farewell function was conducted within the Department of Library and Information Science at the end of October 2022 as Prof. S.Ravi was retiring from his teaching career. The department level function was organised by the final year P.G students and PhD scholars in coordination with all the teaching and non teaching staff members of the department.

Professor S. Ravi being the guest of honour was felicitated by each and every staff. The head of the department Dr. Akhandanand Shukla honoured professor S.Ravi with a shawl. A heartwarming and touching acceptance speech was delivered by Prof. S.Ravi at the end of the function. The function was concluded with a sweet song by Ravi sir himself.

In addition to the department level function, School level function was organised by the Dean of School of Communication, Prof. G. Ravindran combining both the departments of Media & Mass Communication as well as the Department of Library and Information Science.

Dr. Suseela Ravi Endowment for Library and Information Science in CUTN

Prof. S. Ravi has endowed Two Lakhs rupees for the creation of an endowment in the name of his wife, Dr. Suseela Ravi. The endowment has been titled as 'Suseela Ravi Endowment in Library and Information Science' to award a suitable medal to the first rank holder of the Master's Degree in Library and Information Science at CUTN every year in the annual convocation. Prof. S. Ravi also added that Library Science was always his beloved subject that possess the immense potentiality for academic and social good. The Department of Library and Information Science was started in 2017 and he had been privileged to become the first Professor and Head of the Department as well as the Dean, School of Communication.

NSIL Conference 2022

Innovative Librarianship : A Foresight on Aatmanirbhar Bharat

The Central Library, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur has organized the ICSSR Sponsored National Seminar on *INNOVATIVE LIBRARIANSHIP: A Foresight on Aatmanirbhar Bharath (NSIL-2022)* on 29th & 30th July, 2022. The conference objectively provided a platform to present and discuss the latest developments and applications related to sustainable development in the field of Library & Information Science. Research papers, conceptual papers, and cases were presented at the event by academicians, library professionals, research scholars, and library and information science students, relevant to the theme of the conference. Prof. M. Krishnan, the Vice Chancellor, CUTN chaired the chief patron of the event and Dr. S. Dhanavandan, Deputy Librarian directed and pursued the convener of the program.

Best Paper Awards- NSIL 2022

PhD scholars of DLIS, Ms. Komal Sahu and Ms. Rima Hazarika awarded with certificate and memento for the best paper presentations.

AJINA K.T
I M.Lib.I.Sc.

A Decade Later...

A decade later,
Some who came instantly,
By holding the memories,
Memories we had given them...

A decade later,
Some who lost us somewhere,
Some who hadn't great time with us,
Some whom we don't even expect...

A decade later,
How do we become remembered!
Our every little thing in their mind,
The ones those are underlined...

A decade later,
The veils so created,
Crushed by the moment,
The light of love spreads...

MOHINI PANDEY
I M.Lib.I.Sc.

DAD

A father's love, a guiding light,
In every moment, day and night.
A steady hand, a heart of Gold,
A storyteller, wise and bold.

He teaches us, with gentle ease,
The lessons that will last a lifetime.
With patience, grace and dignity,
He leads us to the path that's right.

A shoulder to cry on, a helping hand,
A safe heaven in life's rough sea.
A father's love is always grand,
A precious gift, a legacy.

So, here's to you, my dear father,
The one who made me who I am.
With love and gratitude, then and now,
Forever in my heart and mind!!

FATHIMA S
II M.Lib.I.Sc.

SOWMYAMOL U.S
I M.Lib.I.Sc.

Placement

MS. NAMITHA P

- MLIS graduated student (2020-2022).
- Appointed as Library Trainee at the Indian Institute of Management (IIM) , Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu.

MS. PAPIT PARITHA A

- MLIS graduated student (2019-2021).
- Appointed as Librarian at the MASS College of Education, Kumbakonam, M.A.S Subbaiah Chettiar Educational & Charitable Trust.

MS. YAZHINI R

- MLIS graduated student (2020-2022).
- Appointed as Librarian at Rabiammal Ahamed Maideen College for Women, Thiruvarur (affiliated to Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu).

MS. DAMALLA ROHINI

- MLIS graduated student (2018-2020).
- Appointed as Library Intern at Shreenivas Deshpande Library of Indian Institute of Technology, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi (IIT BHU).

MS. GREESHMA G

- MLIS graduated student (2020-2022).
- Appointed as Library Trainee at the Indian Institute of Information Technology, Design and Manufacturing (IIITDM), Kancheepuram, Chennai.

MS. SARMISHTA RAGHAVAN

- MLIS graduated student (2020-2022).
- Appointed as Library Trainee at the Central University of Kerala, Kasargod.

MS. JOONA THOMMI

- MLIS graduated student (2018-2020).
- Appointed as Librarian (on contract) at Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya, Silvassa, UT of Dadra & Nagar Haveli.

MS. AISWARYA M

- MLIS graduated student (2020-2022).
- Appointed as Library Trainee at the Central University of Kerala, Kasargod.

MR. MATOOR UDAY KIRAN

- MLIS graduated student (2020-2022).
- Appointed as Professional Assistant at the Learning Resource Centre, Indian School of Business (ISB), Hyderabad Campus.

MS. AYSHA MAHIRA C M

- MLIS graduated student (2020-2022).
- Appointed as Library Trainee at the Institute of Mathematical Sciences, CIT Campus, Taramani, Chennai.

Dil ka Makaan

Meri hasi ke peeche
chupe kaafi raaz bhi hai,

Raaton ke andhero me
parchai si gum meri awaaz bhi hai,

In ankhoh me nahi par
meri likhai me uski sajawat aj bhi hai,

Maana jarjar hai dil ka makaan mera
par dabi kisi kone me uski
mohabbat aaj bhi hai....

HARIS PERWAIZ
I M.Lib.I.Sc.

I believe along

I try to breathe
but air burns my lungs;
And I believe along with it
I suck the yellow out of the sun,
leaving it nothing but eclipsed..
I try to speak
but words die on my tongue;
And I believe along with them
I gulp down the water from the oceans,
leaving nothing but drought in my wake.
I try to sleep
but nightmares coat my eyes;
And I believe along with them
I freeze the burning stars in the sky,
leaving nothing but a blackened abyss.
I try to be happy
but life never played fair with me;
And believe along with it
I lost the will to live,
leaving nothing but a shell of person I used
to be.
I try,
but it's never enough. Nor am I.

K. C. VARMA
II M.Lib.I.Sc.

Padma Shri Palam Kalyanasundaram: The Man Of The Millenium

Kalyanasundaram, a true humanitarian, a gold medalist in library science, he also holds a masters degree in literature and history. During his 35-year-long career at Kumarkurupara Arts College at Srivaikuntam, he diligently and willingly donated his salary month after month towards charity and did odd jobs to meet his daily needs.

Even after retirement, he worked as a waiter in a hotel in exchange for two meals a day and a meagre salary so that he could continue to donate to orphanages and to children's educational funds.

Through his three-decade career as a librarian in Thoothukudi, 'Palam' Kalyana Sundaram gave away all his earnings to charity and later formed the social welfare organisation 'Palam'.

Reacting to his being chosen for the Padma Shri award, Mr. Sundaram said that this would only motivate him to continue his service for the betterment of the people.

Always Thinking of the End of 'EDUCATION'

FATHIMA S
II M.Lib.I.Sc.

With the birth of a child, his future is also being written. What to eat, what to do, how to behave, and what job to get will be decided in advance.

Attempts to repeat letters and words are demonstrated as soon as they begin to speak. Start learning letters and words at 3 years of age. Records say that a 7-year-old child became literate. The point is that he can read, write, and understand. A child who becomes literate at the age of 7 has to be checked to see if he completes his education later on.

A look at the streets across the country shows a large number of official and unofficial establishments. In this age where education is a priority, one has to wonder if a child is getting a complete education.

The ruling government has different policies to protect the rights of every citizen. Most of the policies are not fully implemented. Private firms are also looking to capitalise on the flexibility of many.

A government employee competes for thousands of dollars in order to become a private school teacher. A good percentage of them are hired from the audience because they think they are the best. The most highly educated and most competitive, yet a student who has completed 12 long years of primary education does not have the guts to even assert who he is, and parents today want most students to study in English medium. Yet one must wonder why one cannot speak to someone in English without hesitation and without making mistakes.

A student spends most of his time in a day, except for sleeping time, with the teacher. For a student, school is their second home. Yet whose problem is it that they have to rely on tuition centers to understand what is taught in schools? Teachers who believe that life is safe after getting a government job, parents who believe that their children can fully understand what they are studying if tuition is available, or students who believe that they can go to tuition and study even if they do not listen to the teachers. The Constitution of India recognises every person over the age of 18 as a citizen. But how many 18-year-olds can sweetly say who they are in a public congregation? How many people can say "no" with firm determination when they should say "no"? How many people can publicly question those who encroach on their rights? All of these are examples of significant educational gaps.

A private institution will teach a person who can't write and speak English without mistakes in 3 months, even after studying for 15 years. Having studied up to the 12th grade, when a competitive exam comes up, one has to rely on a private institution. When education becomes a business, the difference in money interferes with the dreams of many students.

"If you look at the streets across the country, there are too many technical and non-technical institutions. Is a child getting a complete education in this age of emphasis on education?"

A Friend Point of View

Tumne usko haste dekha
 Maine usko rote dekha
 Aankhe hai ek par
 Najriya hai alag
 Kyunki usse hamara rista bhi hai alag
 Tumne usko haste dekha
 Maine usko til til kar siskate dekha
 Tumhare bare me bate kar kar karke pakata hai bahut
 Tumhare bare me bate kar kar karke pakata hai bahut
 Aur Tumhare ruthane se darta bhi hai bahut
 Tumne usko haste dekha
 Maine usko til til kar marte dekha

SHIVENDRA SHEKHAR
 II M.Lib.I.Sc.

TRUST

Knowledge is Power.
 Power comes with Time.
 And gives Experiences.
 Experience gives Maturity.
 Maturity helps to understand
 between Right and Wrong.
 And after all these things
 we are able for TRUST
 So Trust is the most expensive thing in the World

If you visit a library, try to read atleast one page since your future will be decided then...

-K. Chennakesavulu

What If...?

There are many things in the world we see that we seldom pay attention to. If we find some time to observe and just think about it for a minute, it might make sense. These things might be scientifically "ERROR". But do you really care about what the scientific community says?

ABHISHEK M
II M.Lib.I.Sc.

People who watch the fantasy and animation movies are saying this, "It's not scientifically correct". The fact is, we all like to live in the world of imagination. Then why do you care to live in someone else's imagination while you can create a whole bunch of your own. After all great scientific discoveries have been evolved from the grave mistakes and accidents happened in the history; who knows, may be from a stupid imagination.

Let us just go through the discovery of gravity. Sir Isaac Newton, one of the great scientists of his time, who has formulated the laws and equations relating gravity. How do you think he did it? How does he arrive at all these conclusions?

Let me guess what you are gonna say;

Newton was sitting under an apple tree. He dozed off when the cold breeze embraced him, the breeze didn't forget to fondle the apple that was hanging above poor Newton's head. The apple fell...Oh! Let me make a grammatical mistake, The apple fell "DOWN" on Newton's head.

Newton: " Hey ,it's an apple, it fell down, it didn't fly up.

Eureka...! (Oh I'm sorry it was Archimedes who yelled that.)

Hurray...! I invented a downward force. Let's name it gravity. BOOM..!

$F = G \frac{Mm}{r^2}$ - Just ignore it! it's just a useless equation to create simple physics problems viz. Find the mass of the sun if a two year old baby drives a supercar at a speed of 220 km/hr, hits an old woman, crashes on an apple tree at a force of 2000 Newtons and they both live happily ever after. Find the force at which an apple fell from the tree on the head of Newton who was sitting on the other side...and the mass of the sun too!

This is not what happened actually. This is the part where the magic word came into play...

"What if ?"

Newton just sat there thinking about the attractive force that made the Apple fall. The next moment he thought was about the whole solar system, not why the apple didn't fly up.

"What if the moon is attracted and being held closed the earth with the same force that allows the Apple to fall down and holds himself on the ground?"

"What if all the planets are held in its orbits by the same attractive force to the sun?"

"What if all of us attracting something else around us?"

These were his sequence of thoughts. These thoughts helped him to arrive in some great conclusions that lead to the discovery of facts about weakest force in nature, the "Gravitational Force".

So, my question is why don't we discover anything? Why don't the accidents happening to us end up in some discoveries / inventions? Are you seriously gonna answer that question with an excuse like we are no scientists or with a question like aren't we just ordinary people..?

No, that's not the actual reason. Issac Newton and Albert Einstein were not born as scientists, both of them were below average students in primary classes. The great Stephen Hawking was not at all supposed to write papers on the vast endless universal abnormalities and black holes. The real reason is that we are not observing. We are not thinking in the way we are supposed to. Our stream of consciousness is flowing in a very stupid way. The thing is, we have to train our mind so as to become a "someone"

Don't do something motivated from others' doings or words. Get motivated from your own past and by imagining yourself the brightest future.

What if you end up in a very different road that is gonna lead you to a very happy destination? The one in which you will be smiling wholeheartedly at some point thinking about all the hard decisions and fruitful observations you have ever came across.

What if you could change your destiny with one minute observation?
What if....?

Hindi Fortnight Competitions, 2022

Dr. V. K. Dhanyasree, Assistant Professor, Department of Library and Information Science has received prizes in the different events organised by the Hindi Cell, Central University of Tamil Nadu on the occasion of Hindi Fortnight Competitions 2022. The winnings are listed as follows.

Hindi Administrative Glossary/Noting Writing Competition	- Second Prize
Hindi Handwriting Competition	- Second Prize
Hindi Extract Reading Competition	- Third Prize
Hindi Dumb Charades Competition	- Second Prize

Faculty Activities

PUBLICATION LIST

Dr. Akhandanand Shukla

Journals – International / National (Peer Reviewed & Indexed / Abstracted)

Das, T K, Behera, M, Makwana, J & Shukla, Akhandanand. (2022). Scientometric Discovery of Research Contributions of the Journal “Nature Climate Change” during 2011–2020. *Library Herald*. 60(3), 51–67.

Moyon, NG Thermi, Shukla, Akhandanand, Ngurtinkhuma, R K, Ravi, S. (2022). Scientometric Mapping of Library and Information Science Research among SAARC Countries during 2012–2021. *RBU Journal of Library and Information Science*. 24. 30–36.

Maurya, Sanjay Kumar, Shukla, Akhandanand & Ngurtinkhuma, R. K. (2022). Research Output of LIS Faculty Members of Central Universities of India: An Assessment. *IASLIC Bulletin*. 67(1), 41–52.

Conference Proceedings – International

Das, T. K., Makwana, J.C. & Shukla, Akhandanand. (2022). Quantitative analysis of scientific literature on climate change in India: A scientometric study. In Babbar, P. et al. (Eds.), 16th COLLNET Conference 2022 on “Metrics, Indicators, Mapping and Data Visualizations in Webometrics, Informetrics and Scientometrics” (pp. 398–408). Delhi: B K Books International.

Books (Edited)

Sivaraman, P., Vijayakumar, K., Shukla, Akhandanand, Sanjeevi, K., Natarajan, R. (2022). Recent Perspective on Technology Transfer in Library Science Education (Edited Volume). Polur, Tamil Nadu: Vivekanandha International Book Publishers. ISBN – 978-81-956952-6-3.

Book Chapters (Edited / Festschrift Volumes)

Sahu, Komal & Shukla, Akhandanand. (2022). E-learning: an approach headed towards making Atmanirbhar Bharat. In Goswami M. P. et al. (Eds.), *Atmanirbhar Bharat and Media: On the Road to Success*(pp. 56–66). New Delhi: Today & Tomorrow’s Printers and Publishers.

Kumar, Praveen & Shukla, Akhandanand. (2022). Role of libraries in self-reliant India. In Goswami M. P. et al. (Eds.), *Atmanirbhar Bharat and Media: On the Road to Success* (pp. 96-105). New Delhi: Today & Tomorrow's Printers and Publishers.

Sahu, Komal & Shukla, Akhandanand. (2022). Open Access Tools and Services Provided by the Academic Institutions Libraries during COVID-19 Pandemic. In Dhanavandan S. (Ed.), *Ingenious Librarianship: Enriching Self-Reliance*. New Delhi: Today and Tomorrow Printers and Publishers.

Sahu, Komal & Shukla, Akhandanand. (2022). Research Data Management: Role of Academic Libraries. In Sivaraman, P. et al. (Eds.), *Recent Perspectives on Technology Transfer in Library Science Education*. Polur, Tamil Nadu: Vivekanandha International Book Publishers.

Aysha Mahira, C.M. & Shukla, Akhandanand. (2022). Use of library website as a resource among the postgraduate students of Central University of Tamil Nadu. In Dhanavandan S. (Ed.), *Digital Librarianship and Social Media* (pp. 61-67). New Delhi: Studera Press.

Sahu, Komal & Shukla, Akhandanand. (2022). Digital revolution and electronic resource management systems in libraries. In Dhanavandan S. (Ed.), *Innovative Librarianship: Impetus to Digital Convergence* (pp. 161-170). New Delhi: Today and Tomorrow Printers and Publishers.

Kumar, Praveen & Shukla, Akhandanand. (2022). Entrepreneurship practices in India with special reference to library services. In Dhanavandan S. (Ed.), *Innovative Librarianship: Accelerating Open Access* (pp. 165-172). New Delhi: Today and Tomorrow Printers and Publishers.

Worked as a Resource Person/Session Chaired/Invited Talk

Resource person for UGC-HRDC sponsored Refresher Course in Library & Information Science, organized by Pondicherry University held on 31.01.2023.

Resource person for UGC-HRDC sponsored Short Term Course on "MOOCs: A Vertical Pedagogy for Asynchronous Learning", organized by Department of Library & Information Science, Jadavpur University, Kolkata held on 30.01.2023.

Resource person for UGC-HRDC sponsored Refresher Course in Library & Information Science, organized by University of Mysore held on 12.11.2022.

Resource person for UGC-HRDC sponsored Refresher Course in Library & Information Science, organized by Mizoram University, Aizawl held on 12.10.2022.

Invited speaker for the RRRLF sponsored National Conference on Changing Information Landscape and Its Transformation in LIS Education (NCTLISE-2022) held on 2nd – 3rd September 2022, organized by Department of Library and Information Science, Alagappa University, Karaikudi.

Chaired a session in ICSSR Sponsored Two Day National Seminar on “Innovative Librarianship: A Foresight on Atmanirbhar Bharat (NSIL-2022)” organized by Central Library, Central University of Tamil Nadu on 29th – 30th July 2022.

Chaired a session in ICSSR Sponsored Two Day National Seminar on “Atmanirbhar Bharat and Media: on the Road to Success” organized by Department of Media & Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu.

Dr. Taddi Murali

Murali, T. (2022) Reading Culture and Changing Technological Environment Journal of Electronic Information Technology and Management, 12(9). <http://jeitsm.com/>ISSN NO: 0258-7982

Dr. K G. Sudhier

Books (Edited)

Sivaraman, P., et al Eds. (2022). Recent Perspective on Technology Transfer in Library Science Education. Polur, Tamil Nadu: Vivekanandha International Book Publishers. ISBN - 978-81-956952-6-3 [Associate Editor].

Journal Articles (Indexed and Peer Reviewed)

Suman Barath, P & Sudhier. K G. (2022). User perception on e-resources and information services in a public library: A study of Kerala state central library. Annals of Library and Information Studies, 69 (4), 2022: 277-281. DOI: 10.56042/alis.v69i4.64900

Hazarika, Rima & Sudhier. K G. Research Trend of Assamese Language and Literature: A Bibliometric study based on Shodhganga. ILIS Journal of Librarianship and Informatics, 5 (1), 2022.

Suman Barath, P & Sudhier, K G. Role of Public Libraries in Bridging the Digital Divide: A Review Literature. *ILIS Journal of Librarianship and Informatics*, 5 (2), 2022.

Soman, V. S. Midhula & Sudhier, K. G. (2022). Library and information needs of Differently-abled students in Kerala: a study. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 7333. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7333>

Seminar & Conference Presentations

Abhijith, B and Sudhier, K G. (2022). Content delivery networks (CDN) for library websites : A study. International conference on Emerging digital library platforms: Shaping digital transformation and national data exchange (ICEDLP), August 9-12, 2022. DRTC, Indian Statistical Institute, Bangalore. [Proceeding edited by M. Krishnamurthy et. al., Bangalore: DRTC, 2022. pp.663-669. ISBN 978 93 5680 830 0].

Hazarika, Rima & Sudhier, K G. A bibliometric study of the Journal of Social Sciences (2019- 2020). National Seminar on Innovative Librarianship: A foresight on Atmanirbhar Bharat (NCIL-2022). 29-30 July 2022. ICSSR & CUTN Central Library, Thiruvavur.

Book Chapters (Edited / Festschrift Volumes)

Hazarika, Rima & Sudhier, K G. (2022). A Webometrics Analysis of Selected State University Websites in Assam. In *Changing Information Landscape and its Transformation in LIS Education*. S. Thanuskodi & R. Jeyshankar, Eds. Karaikudi: Alagappa University, 2022. pp.342-350. ISBN : 978-93-92990-12-0.

Suman Barath, P and Sudhier, K G. Evolution of the Public Library system in Tamil Nadu. In *Recent Perspectives on Technology transfer in Library Science Education*. P. Sivaraman et al., Eds. Annamalai Nagar: Dept. of Library & Information Science, Annamalai University, 2022. pp. 219-226. ISBN 978-81-956952-6-3.

Hazarika, Rima and Sudhier, K G. Scientometric portrait of Prof. S. Ravi: A distinguished Professor of Library and Information Science. In *Recent Perspectives on Technology transfer in Library Science Education*. P. Sivaraman et al., Eds. Annamalai Nagar: Dept. of Library & Information Science, Annamalai University, 2022. pp. 133-140. ISBN 978-81-956952-6-3.

Popular Articles

Global academic rankings and Indian universities. *Lib Space- Library News letter of the Sree Sankara College, Kalady*; November 2022, 01 (2); 12-14.

Resource Person/Session Chaired/Invited Talk

Invited speaker for the National Symposium on 'Relevance of Libraries and Higher Education Research' organized by the DLIS, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirapalli, in association with Indian Social Science Academy (ISSA), Allahabad held on 12th August 2022.

Invited speaker for the Tamil Nadu Academic Library Association (TNALA) sponsored three days multidisciplinary International Conference on 'Emerging Information Knowledge System and Globalisation of Higher Education' (MTWU-TNLA-CONF 2022), held on 24-26 November 2022 held at Mother Teresa Women's University, Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu.

Chaired a session for the RRRLF sponsored National Conference on Changing Information Landscape and Its Transformation in LIS Education (NCTLISE-2022) held on 2nd - 3rd September 2022, organized by Department of Library and Information Science, Alagappa University, Karaikudi.

Chaired a session in ICSSR Sponsored Two Day National Seminar on "Innovative Librarianship: A Foresight on Atmanirbhar Bharat (NSIL-2022)" organized by Central Library, Central University of Tamil Nadu on 29th - 30th July 2022.

Resource person for UGC-HRDC sponsored Refresher Course in Library & Information Science, organized by the Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati, Maharashtra held on 17 September 2022.

Resource person for UGC-HRDC sponsored Refresher course in Malayalam language & Literature, organized by the Kerala University, Trivandrum held on 25-08-2022.

Resource person for UGC-HRDC sponsored Faculty Induction Programme, organized by the Kannur University, Kerala held on 13-10-2022.

Resource person for UGC-HRDC sponsored Faculty Induction Programme, organized by the Kannur University, Kerala held on 23-11-2022.

Dr. Anila Sulochana

Nayanthara, S and Sulochana, Anila. Open Science: Global Position and Share of India. (2022). In proceedings of International CALIBER-2022, INFLIBNET

<http://ir.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/1944/2399>

Newspaper Clippings

Revamped Anna Centenary Library gets ready to attract young readers

To Hold Talk Shows, Kids' Festivals

Ragu.Raman@timesgroup.com

Chennai: Brand new toilets, refurbished floors, a new LED wall, high-quality air conditioning, new furniture and special light settings are set to welcome the readers at Anna Centenary Library from the second week of November.

With the restoration work nearing completion, the library is planning to attract the young readers and kids with various new programmes and events including a new talk series 'TN Talk' by international authors, scientists and a kids festival in this month. A vir-

CHILDREN'S DELIGHT

Restoration cost | ₹38 crore
Facilities include | New toilets, refurbished floors and roofs, a LED wall, new furniture and special light settings, sound systems
More in offing | Virtual Reality section and food

court will be added in coming months
Collection books | More than 6 lakh e-books | 3,000
In pipeline | TN Talk, a new talk series and a kids festival in November

A revamped section for kids at the library

tual reality library in the kids section, latest computers, a food court for serving quality food at subsidised cost will be further additions to the world-class library in the coming months.

The library currently has a collection of 6.2lakh books and access to 3000 e-books. The process of procuring new books and adding e-books collection also began.

The government allotted ₹38crore to refurbish the li-

brary. "We expect the entire library will be restored by the second week of November," said K Elambavath, director of public libraries (full additional charge).

The library attracts 2,000 to 2,500 visitors a day. A majority of them are students and civil service aspirants.

"The storytelling corner and kids section are attracting more kids every week. We are planning to start a kids festival on Sundays in

November with storytelling, fancy dress and drawing, painting competitions," he added.

The new talk series 'TN Talk' is planned to be launched in the third week of November. It will also restart its 'Ponmalai Pozhudhu' event after restoration.

The library has a vast collection of books on various topics including medicine, engineering, agriculture, management, law, econom-

ics, veterinary science, earth science, computer science, statistics, social science, religion, psychology, maths and astronomy. It also has an entire floor dedicated to Tamil books.

"There is a lack of awareness among students about the reference books available at the library. We are planning to conduct events with various academic institutions to encourage more students to use the books in the library," Elambavath said.

The renovated auditorium and conference halls with new lighting, sound systems and projectors will be rented out to academic institutions and other organisations to conduct conference, seminars. The 300-capacity open air theatre will be given to performing arts groups at a subsidised cost.

State Library Committee reconstituted

The Hindu Bureau
CHENNAI

After more than a decade, the Tamil Nadu government issued orders reconstituting the State Library Committee and the Local Library Authority for Chennai city, said Minister for School Education Anbil Mahesh Poyyamozhi on Sunday.

In a statement, Mr. Poyyamozhi said the 15-member State Library Committee includes the School Education Minister, Minister for Rural Development, three legislators, expert G. Gopanna, Tamil Nadu Library Association's G. Rathinasabapathy, Madras Library Association's K. Nithyanandam, Director of Roja Muthiah Research Library G. Sundar. The library authority had been reconstituted with 11 members.

'Learn Tamil' books fly off the shelves

With Hindi speakers as well as Tamil-origin residents of Varanasi eagerly picking up self-learning books at exhibition in Banaras Hindu University, where Kashi Tamil Sangamam is on, organisers have to replenish stocks every two days

Jagriti Chandra
VARANASI

Books on learning to speak, read and write Tamil are the hottest selling books at an exhibition being held at the Banaras Hindu University (BHU), the venue for the ongoing month-long Kashi Tamil Sangamam.

The book stall, set up by the Central Institute of Indian Languages (CIIL) under the Ministry of Education, includes self-learning books in 11 languages under its "Bhasha Jyoti" initiative.

"Our books on learning Tamil as a second language are by far the most popular ones. We didn't expect this kind of response," said CIIL

High demand! A stall put up at Banaras Hindu University as part of the Kashi Tamil Sangamam. SPECIAL ARRANGEMENT

Director Shalendra Mo-

han. "We run out of our stock of books on Tamil every two days, and have to bring more books from our centre in Mysuru. We have

sold nearly 500 Tamil learning books since the exhibition opened on November 19. There is a lot of interest from Hindi speaking customers, as well as from Tamil-origin resi-

dents who know how to speak the language, but can't write in it," said Frank Dhwedi, Junior Research Fellow at CIIL, who is overseeing the stall.

While purchasing Tamil books, Varanasi resident Varun Mishra, 29, said: "We often travel to southern parts of the country in search of jobs, but we face language-centric conflicts at every turn." Mr. Mishra works at a private bank in Bengaluru.

"We shouldn't have extremism around languages, after all people like me who originate from Bihar too have left behind Bhojpuri and Maghad and embraced Hindi and are also open to embracing other Indian languages," he said.

A happy family taking home their book haul from the Cincinnati Library bookmobile in 1940.

TN govt sanctions ₹84cr to repair rural libraries

Ram.Sundaram
@timesgroup.com

Chennai: The Tamil Nadu government has sanctioned another ₹84 crore to repair 3,800 rural libraries which are in bad shape without proper maintenance.

Ten years ago, the rural development department under the Anaiathu Grama Anna Marumalarchi Thittam (AGAMT) started building 12,525 libraries in all villages.

Considered late chief minister M Karunanidhi's signature project, the then DMK government purchased books worth several lakhs for these libraries, benefiting students, women and senior citizens, who couldn't travel to the respective district headquarters to access public libraries.

In the next two years, many libraries were locked as enough funds were not sanctioned. In 2015, barely 2,000

TOTAL EXPENSE

Work	Cost (₹ in crore)
Repairing buildings	55.71
Providing furniture	9.52
Buying new books	19.04

were functioning and for only three days a week. Books began gathering dust and the buildings in some villages became havens for anti-social elements.

Almost after a decade, chief minister M K Stalin revived the AGAMT and sanctioned ₹91 crore for repairing 4,116 rural libraries. Now, rural development secretary P Amudha has released another ₹84 crore to renovate another 3,808 libraries this year.

Officials said every library will be allotted ₹50,000 for new books whose purchase will be decided by a state-level committee.

Though this can be used only for books, the honorary librarian, engaged by village panchayat libraries, and collectors should ensure that newspapers and magazines too are available with the help of NGOs or corporate houses, Amudha's November 3 order said.

Dr Thirunukkarsu, a librarian, said, many who prepare for competitive exams do not have a place to sit and prepare. "If these rural libraries can be repaired and put to use, it will be of great help."

K Nithyanandam of the Madras Library Association said this will help improve the reading habit among young children, particularly those who can't afford to spend more on new books.

MAMIDALA JAGADESH KUMAR

The age of innovation

New UGC rules will encourage students to enter PhD courses at an early age

SAMIR V Kansar, DRDO chairman, obtained his Btech (Hons) in 1985 from IIT Kharagpur and, in the next three years, completed his PhD from the Ohio State University in 1988. Amit Kumar at IIT Delhi did his Btech from IIT Kanpur in 1997 and obtained his PhD in 2002 from Cornell University. He is a Bhatnagar Award winner. Shubham Sahay at IIT Kanpur obtained his Btech from IIT (BHU) in 2014 and a PhD from IIT Delhi in 2018. At IIT Kanpur, students have routinely rated his teaching as outstanding.

I can cite any number of cases from our higher education institutes (HEIs) of outstanding teachers and researchers minus a PG degree. Globally too, we have many such examples.

Robert Burns Woodward entered MIT in 1933 for his UG programme but was excluded from MIT at the end of the fall term in 1934 due to a lack of attention to formal studies. Later he was allowed to re-enroll in the fall term of 1935. Woodward obtained the UG degree in 1936 and a PhD degree in 1937. He was awarded the 1965 Nobel Prize in chemistry.

It is not true that PhDs who have bypassed the PG degree will have inadequate knowledge of the core discipline, which will lead to degrading teaching or research standards. We may tend to dismiss the above examples as coming from top institutes such as IITs, Purdue, and MIT.

Let us not underestimate the talent that is present in the university ecosystem of India. Since our admission processes are by elimination rather than selection due to intense competition, a huge pool of highly talented students who could not get into top HEIs is part of the university system. Once we provide the opportunity to the passionate students among these to move into a PhD programme after their UG degree, they will have the chance to blossom into outstanding teachers or researchers.

By keeping our University educational system too rigid, we are only keeping many talented students from reaching the pinnacle of their real potential. That is why the University Grants Commission (UGC) has announced the new four-year UG programme and flexible PhD regulations permitting these students with four-year UG degrees to join PhD programmes.

Getting into a PhD programme is also a long commitment requiring determination and hard work. The option of doing a PhD is only for those with the potential, passion, and focus for high attainment in a specific discipline. The goal of UGC in permitting students after a UG degree into PhD programmes is not numbers but quality.

As per NEP 2020, the four-year undergraduate programme offers an honours degree with the last year dedicated to research or an honours degree with a primary focus on coursework. The new regulations will permit students from both categories to join PhD degree programmes. But how can students who have not chosen the research path in the fourth year be admitted to a PhD programme? After a four-year course-based UG programme, the student may work on an industry or university research project and gain research experience. Such students, too, should get an opportunity to join a PhD programme without being forced to do a PG degree. Or they can be trained in research methods during the beginning of their PhD programme.

In the UGC's new PhD regulations, anyone who has completed a four-year bachelor's degree programme in any discipline with a minimum of 75 per cent marks in agree-

programme. UGC prescribes only the minimum qualifications for admission to a PhD programme. Universities can raise the bar to ensure that only the deserving are admitted to PhD programmes.

The four-year bachelor's degree programme introduced in our university system is designed to equip the students with complex problem-solving, critical thinking, creative thinking, and communication skills. This training will accompany rigorous specialisation in a chosen disciplinary or interdisciplinary major and minor subject area.

A research study on the Nobel Prizes in chemistry, physiology, or medicine between 1901 and 2003 indicates that the majority of the winners who discovered their prize-winning results were aged between 31 and 40. Our creativity declines with ageing in most of us. India has almost 250 million students between 15 and 25 years old. The best among these need to be encouraged to get into research and innovation at an early age after their UG degree when their creativity levels are on an ascending trajectory if India has to become a world leader in research and innovation.

The writer is chairman, UGC and AICTE.

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